

Received / Makale Geliş Tarihi 03.09.2024
Published / Yayınlanma Tarihi 30.11.2024
Volume (Issue) Cilt (Sayı) 8 (48)
pp / ss 1435-1447

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.14266464
Mail: editor@pejoss.com

Bilim Uzmanı Rana Şat

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0271-9388>
Balıkesir Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Balıkesir/ TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02tv7db43>

Dr. Fatih Saydam

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0271-9388>
Giresun Üniversitesi, Dereli Meslek Yüksekokulu, Giresun/ TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/05sraq822>

**A Research on the Use of Geographically Marked Products by Local Businesses:
The Case of Giresun Province**

**Yerel İşletmelerin Coğrafi İşaretli Ürünleri Kullanımına Yönelik Bir Araştırma:
Giresun İli Örneği**

ABSTRACT

It is aimed to determine the inclusion of local and geographical indication registered food and beverage products in the menus of food and beverage establishments operating in Giresun in the context of gastronomy tourism. In the context of the research, first of all, it is aimed to determine the registered products specific to Giresun Province and the geographical indication products that are in the application process. Afterwards, the usage status of these products in enterprises was analyzed by examining 265 restaurant establishments serving in Giresun Province on TripAdvisor and their usage status and guest comments were analyzed. The sample was obtained by purposive sampling among the food and beverage establishments in Giresun province by determining the food and beverage establishments in the top 20 and having the most comments and evaluations. In data collection, comments are analyzed through document review and content analysis. Accordingly, 265 food and beverage establishments and guest comments were analyzed through content analysis. In this context, 265 food and beverage businesses and guest comments were examined with content analysis. As a result of the research findings, it was seen that products with geographical indications such as Giresun hazelnut paste kadayı dessert, Giresun nettle soup, Görele ice cream were included in the restaurant menus, but local products and dishes such as cheese pide, minced meat pide, kashar kavurma pide, rasatan famous pide, beet soup, mushroom kavurma, corn bread, sirgan yağlaşı, pickle kavurma,

Milk Kadayıf Dessert, bean pickle Roast, anchovy pilaf, cabbage Dible, cabbage sarma, thorn tip, sakarca Roast, nettle mantı, merulcan, taftan salting, cherry salting did not have geographical indications. In addition, it is observed that the comments of the guests about Giresun pide, pickle roast, corn bread, anchovy pilaf, lahna dible, sakarca roast, thorn tip and sakarca roast, merulcan roast, taftan and cherry salting are generally shaped on food themes. It is suggested that Giresun, which is in the process of applying for a geographical indication, should be registered and included in the menus. In addition, the importance of other potential local products such as, which do not have a geographical indication but should be included in the menus, is emphasized. As a result, it has been concluded that the use of geographically indicated products in the menu creates awareness that contributes to the promotion of the Giresun region and the development of gastronomy tourism potential.

Keywords: Geographical Indication, Giresun, Food and Beverage Enterprises, TripAdvisor.

ÖZET

Giresun ilinde faaliyet gösteren yiyecek ve içecek işletmelerinin yöresel ve coğrafi işaret tescilli yiyecek ve içecek ürünlerinin menülerinde yer verilme durumunun, gastronomi turizmi bağlamında tespit edilmesi amaçlanmıştır. Araştırma bağlamında, öncelikle Giresun İline özgü tescilli ve başvuru sürecinde olan coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin tespit edilmesi amaçlanmıştır. Daha sonrasında bu ürünlerin işletmelerdeki kullanım durumu TripAdvisor'da yer alan 265 Giresun İli özelinde hizmet veren restoran işletmeleri incelenerek kullanım durumları ve misafir yorumları analiz edilmiştir. Giresun ilinde yer alan yiyecek içecek işletmeleri arasından amaçlı örnekleme yoluyla ilk 20 içerisinde yer alan ve en çok yoruma, değerlendirmeye sahip yiyecek içecek işletmelerinin belirlenmesiyle örnekleme elde edilmiştir. Verilerin toplanmasında doküman incelemesi ve içerik analiziyle yorumların analiz edilmesi sağlanmaktadır. Bu doğrultuda, 265 yiyecek içecek işletmesi ve misafir yorumu içerik analiziyle incelenmiştir. Araştırma bulguları neticesinde, Giresun fındık ezmeli kadayı tatlısı, Giresun ısırgan otu çorbası, Görele dondurması gibi coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin restoran menülerinde yer aldığını, ancak peynirli pide, kıymalı pide, kaşar kavurmalı pide, rasathane meşhur pidesi, pancar çorbası, mantar kavurma, mısır ekmeği, sirgan yağlaşı, turşu kavurması, sütlü kadayıf, fasulye turşusu kavurması, hamsili pilav, lahana, Dible, lahana sarma, diken ucu, sakarca kavurması, ısırganlı mantı, merulcan, taftan tuzlaması, kiraz tuzlaması gibi yöresel ürünlerin ve yemeklerin coğrafi işaret almadığı görülmektedir. Ayrıca, Giresun pidesi, turşu kavurması, mısır ekmeği, hamsili pilav, lahana diblesi, sakarca kavurması, diken ucu ve sakarca kavurmasının, merulcan kavurmasının, taftan ve kiraz tuzlamasının misafirlerin genelde yorumlarının yemek temaları üzerinde şekillendiği görülmektedir. Coğrafi işaret başvuru sürecinde olan Giresun tescillenerek menülerde yer alması gerektiği önerilmektedir. Bunun yanı sıra, ısırgan otu çorbası, peynirli pide, rasathane pidesi, pancar çorbası, hamsili pilav gibi coğrafi işareti bulunmayan, ancak menülerde yer alması gerekli olan diğer potansiyel yerel ürünlerin de önemi vurgulanmaktadır. Sonuç olarak, coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin menülerde kullanılmasının, Giresun anıtımına ve gastronomi turizmi potansiyelinin geliştirilmesine katkı sağladığı yönünde bir farkındalık oluşturduğu sonucuna ulaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Coğrafi İşaret, Giresun, Yiyecek İçecek İşletmeleri, TripAdvisor

1. INTRODUCTION

Gastronomy tourism is seen as a type of alternative tourism that focuses on the discovery of local food and beverages, includes everything from street food and local dishes to fine dining, and people visit a destination specifically to experience local cuisine. In general terms, it is known that gastronomy tourism is related to the local food and beverages that people experience in the regions they visit (Aksoy & Sezgi, 2015). It is important in terms of both improving the experiences of the guests by offering a unique cultural experience in terms of food and beverage, and benefiting the local economy in terms of increasing local income, creating new job opportunities and sustaining the preservation of the local culinary culture tradition. Gastronomy tourism contributes to the preservation of the authenticity and quality of local and regional cuisine, thus contributing to the management of the impact on local resources and providing a competitive alternative between regions in terms of diversifying tourism (Küçükkömürler, Sırvan & Sezgin, 2018; Torusdağ, Önem, Sami & Kızıldemir, 2022; Yurt, Bayraklı & Özengi, 2024). It offers an exciting experience to guests through an important way of discovering the culture of a region through food and drink. Preserving and sustaining the essence of the products belonging to a region and identified with the region contributes to the economic development and acceleration of the development process of the relevant region. Ensuring the sustainability of local products and establishing a gastronomic relationship with the local culture is among the important situations (Dağ, 2020). It also ensures the continuity of traditional products by preserving and standardizing the rich culinary diversity together with production and consumption rituals and transferring it to future generations, revealing the differences between cultures (Mariani, 2021). For this reason, the identification of local dishes and traditional products and the geographical indication registration system have an important role in the protection of the rich culinary culture in Anatolia.

Giresun Province is becoming one of the important destinations in gastronomy routes in Turkey due to the rich products of its culinary culture and the ease of access to local products. Giresun, which is one of the important cities in Turkey due to the diversity in the culture of local cuisine and traditional dishes, is home to 13 different geographical indication registered food and beverage products as of November 2024 (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office (TPMK), 2024). The need for geographical indication registration with the transfer of local dishes and beverages to future generations and the rapidly increasing importance attached to registered products are among the reasons that increase the desire of local and foreign guests to reach the region as a result of the desire to reach interesting products that are unique to the region and identified with the region (Doğancılı, 2020). The fact that the region contributes to the development of the local economy with the tourism industry contributes to increasing the importance of gastronomy tourism for the region. It is foreseen that the income-generating and promotional effect of gastronomy tourism will benefit the relevant region in many ways. In addition to its income-generating and promotional effects, gastronomy tourism is seen to benefit the region in many ways.

In order for destinations to achieve the necessary gains through gastronomy tourism, it is seen that the local food and beverage products offered by the destination become sustainable in accordance with the regional identity of the region. Thanks to national and international activities for gastronomy tourism, which has come to the forefront among alternative tourism types in recent years, it is pioneered to visit different regions for the promotion of local products, to increase the awareness of geographically marked products, to experience foods and beverages specific to the regions and to taste new flavors (Tüfekci, 2016). Sustainability can be achieved by increasing the awareness of local and region-specific food and beverage products and maintaining the standard of the products. In this context, it is seen that there are various promotional and marketing activities on local products for which geographical indication registration procedures have been completed and are still at the application stage. Since the products with geographical indication registration provide an element of attraction within the scope of gastronomy tourism, it is seen that the contribution of the products identified with the region and the region-specific qualities are carried and the contribution of the products identified with the region has a higher income-generating effect compared to other products of the same type (Ertan, 2010; Özdemir & Altıner, 2018). In this context, by including geographical indication registered local foods and beverages in the menus of food and beverage service providers, it is ensured that the revenues of the enterprises and the awareness of local products by visitors are increased.

In the related literature (Avşar & Eryılmaz, 2022; Çavuş & Eker, 2022; Denk & Sanalan Bilici, 2021; Güngör, 2022; Güngör & Kök, 2021; Hazarhun & Tepeci, 2018; Matviichuk, Lepkyi, Daschuk, Sydoruk & Mezentseva, 2022; Mercan & Üzülmez, 2014; Özer, 2021; Pillay, Sigamany & Belwal, 2018; Piramanayagam & Seal, 2022; Rasmi, Phuoc, Othman & Azman, 2022; Sabur & Güneş, 2023; Seal &

Piramanayagam, 2018; Süslü, Eryılmaz & Demir, 2020; Şimşek & Güleç, 2020; Temiz, 2019, Yıldız, 2021), it is possible to mention the existence of many studies that increase the relationship between gastronomic tourism and geographically marked products. However, there is no study in the literature on the inclusion of geographically marked products in local and traditional restaurants for the development of gastronomy tourism in Giresun province. Therefore, it reveals the originality of this research. The main purpose of this study is to reveal the contribution of geographically marked products of Giresun Province to gastronomy tourism by determining their level of inclusion in local restaurants. In the light of this information, the study firstly presents the conceptual framework for geographically marked products and Giresun Cuisine is included. Then, in order to determine the use of geographically marked products in the menus of food and beverage establishments in the province, a field research was conducted to determine the local restaurant establishments and guest comments on the TripAdvisor website and the contribution of the province to gastronomy tourism was interpreted in line with the findings obtained. As a result of the findings obtained from the study, it is thought that it will make a significant contribution to the literature in this field as it is the first systematic research on the use of geographical indication products in Giresun cuisine by food and beverage establishments. In addition, by addressing the utilization process of geographical indications in the context of gastronomy tourism, it is aimed to add new and concrete data to existing studies on the role of local and regional cuisines on tourism and to further reinforce the originality and scientific value of the studies. In line with this information, the main purpose of this study is to determine the inclusion of local and geographical indication registered food and beverage products in the menus of food and beverage establishments operating in Giresun province and registered on TripAdvisor. In line with this purpose, the study examines the relationship between gastronomy tourism and the concept of geographical indication, the general characteristics of Giresun province and its products with geographical indication by examining the menus and visitor comments of TripAdvisor local businesses.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

2.1. The Impact of Geographical Indication Products in Gastronomy Tourism

Gastronomy, which is one of the most basic touristic products (Küçükaltan, 2009), includes the interest in good, quality and local food, traditional cooking art and culinary culture. It is stated that the related concepts of gastronomy and tourism came together in 1983 and that people learn about the cultures of other countries through food and beverages (Ab Karim & Chi, 2010; Belisle, 1983). The fact that individuals who are interested in eating local and traditional food and who do it for pleasure visit these destinations has helped the emergence of the concept of gastronomy tourism (Dilsiz, 2010). The concept of gastronomy tourism was first introduced by Long in 1998 under the name of “culinary tourism” as an idea for guests to try local food and beverages in different cultures (Yarış, 2014). The concept was defined by Long as “a form of tourism carried out to explore the consumption, preparation, presentation and cuisine, meal systems and eating styles of foods belonging to a culinary culture and tradition different from the known” (Akgöl, 2012). According to Yun, Hennessy & Mac Donald (2011), gastronomy tourism is the process of transferring and discovering the culture and history on gastronomy-related activities to have unforgettable experiences. Gastronomy tourism, which forms part of the local and regional food culture as one of the important attraction elements and reasons for preference of guests in destinations (Quan & Wang, 2004), is described as a form of tourism that provides travel motivation and creates a driving force in travel behavior for those who have not experienced local and traditional food and beverage experiences before (Harrington & Ottenbacher, 2010). Hall & Mitchell (2001) define the concept of gastronomy tourism as travel to different destinations for reasons such as learning the history of food and beverages, which have an important value in terms of cultural heritage, how they are made, how they are cooked and tasting them. Looking at the literature, it is possible to mention that there is an expanding literature on gastronomy tourism. Among the topics that have been addressed recently, especially the impact of gastronomy tourism on the local community (Karahan, 2019; Kattiyapornpong, Ditta-Apichai & Chuntamara, 2022; Kodaş & Dikici, 2012; Tuncay & Özcan, 2022), the role of gastronomy in cultural identity and heritage (Çapar & Yenipinar, 2016; De Miguel Molina, De Miguel Molina, Santamarina Campos & Val Segarra Oña, 2016; Figueiredo, 2021; Van Westering, 1999; Yeşilyurt & Kurnaz, 2021), the importance of sustainability in gastronomy (Scarpato, 2003; Yıkılmış, Erdal, Bozgeyik, Levent & Yinanç, 2022) and the potential of gastronomy tourism in terms of promoting intercultural understanding (Belpinar, 2014; Laenko, 2021).

Developments in the field of gastronomy tourism in the world are, in a sense, the result of countries' efforts to create a new market in the field of tourism and increase tourism revenues. With many people traveling to experience local cuisine and learn new culinary techniques, gastronomy tourism has become a growing

trend in recent years (Kiraz & Altun, 2020). In addition to the benefits of increased tourism revenues, it promotes cultural exchange and supports local economies (Kyriakaki, Zagkotsi & Trihas, 2016; Visković & Komac, 2021). It also helps preserve cultural heritage and promote sustainable development by showcasing local food and beverages and the traditional methods used to produce them (Apak & Gürbüz, 2023; Hazarhun & Tepeci, 2018).

Changing lifestyles, deterioration in eating habits and cultural areas, and social and environmental negativities have led people to learn more about the products they consume. The increasing interest of consumers in local and small-scale productions has necessitated the emergence of new approaches in the production and marketing strategies of local products. One of these strategies, geographical indications (Kan, Gülçubuk & Küçükçongar, 2012), is one of the protective tools that “ensure the protection of a product or value within the scope of legal frameworks” (Üner, 2014) created to ensure the continuity of local products by protecting their authenticity. The Turkish Patent and Trademark Office (TURKPATENT) defines a geographical indication (GI) as “a quality mark that indicates and guarantees for consumers the origin of the product, its characteristic features and the connection between the said characteristic features of the product and the geographical area” (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2023b). Şahin (2013), on the other hand, characterizes the geographical indication practice as “a series of legal measures taken to protect local and, in other words, authentic products and to transfer them to future generations intact with the slogan of localness meeting the world”. Geographical indications are signs that indicate that a product is associated with a specific geographical region. They provide consumers with information about the origin, production methods and other characteristics of products. In Europe, agricultural and food products generally receive geographical indications, while in Turkey, food, agricultural, mining, handicraft and industrial products can be registered with geographical indications (Doğan, 2015; Kan et al., 2012). Turkey is a country with a rich cultural heritage where geographical indications are used in many products in the field of gastronomy. For example, pistachio is a product that grows in the special climate and soil conditions of Gaziantep province, has a unique taste and aroma, and has received a geographical indication, indicating that the product is unique to Gaziantep province. Likewise, Aydın figs have also received the geographical indication for their taste, texture and quality. Geographical indication “enables consumers to have detailed information about the origin and quality of the product, to make the right choice and to have a wider selection” (Tekelioğlu, 2019). While geographical indications reassure consumers about the origin of these products, they also aim to protect their cultural and economic value. Products that have gained a certain reputation due to their quality, tradition, raw materials obtained from the region and local qualities are protected by geographical indication registration and can be registered as “name of origin” or “indication of origin” (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Incorporating geographically marked products into local cuisines and menus can enhance the overall gastronomy tourism experience by giving visitors a taste of the region's unique flavors, history and culture. When food and beverage establishments use locally sourced ingredients, this sets them apart from their competitors. This can affect the revisit intention of tourists seeking an authentic culinary experience (Baydeniz, Kılıcı & Çelik, 2023; Çeşmeci, Çulfacı & Kılıçhan, 2023). At the same time, this method, which supports local producers, has a positive economic impact on society (Çeşmeci, Çulfacı & Kılıçhan). The use of GI products in local cuisine provides environmental benefits as it reduces the carbon footprint associated with the transportation of food over long distances, and culturally, it helps to protect the heritage and traditions of the region (Bessière, 1998; Duram & Oberholtzer, 2010; Wakeland, Cholette & Venkat, 2011).

When the studies investigating the relationship between geographical indications and gastronomy tourism in the literature were examined, no study specific to Giresun Cuisine was found. However, there are 12 geographical indication products belonging to Giresun province, two products in the application process and three registered products. Although the widespread use of geographically marked products in Giresun Province is known, it is not known whether they are sufficiently included in the menus of food and beverage establishments and thus their contribution to gastronomy tourism. Based on this idea, in the rest of the study, firstly, Giresun local and geographically marked local cuisine will be introduced and then the findings obtained from the field research will be presented.

2.2. Giresun Cuisine and Local Products

Food culture is an important element as it constitutes the identity of the regions. For this reason, food culture, which is defined as the way of life of a society, has played an important role in the definition of culture in the past and today. “Food culture, which varies from region to region, attracts the attention of

visitors and gastronomy tourism, which is formed in this direction, takes its place among tourism types as a tourist attraction element” (Göker, 2011). According to Long (2004), one of the important elements that distinguish the culture and identity of a region from other regions is the local cuisine. Almost every geographical region has its own culinary culture (Ballı, 2013). Giresun Cuisine is one of the cultures with its own unique characteristics.

Giresun Province, which has hosted many civilizations in the historical process, has a rich cultural heritage. An important aspect of this culture is the local cuisine culture. Due to the fact that Giresun Province, located in the northern region of Anatolia, is a transit center and has different climates and geographies, dishes consisting of herbs, leaves and seafood are dominant in the coastal areas, while pastries based on cereal products and meat dishes based on animal husbandry are predominant in inland districts such as Şebinkarahisar, Alucra and Çamoluk. These differences manifest themselves in equipment, cooking and places. The nature of Giresun is covered with rich vegetation due to the rainfall and abundant humidity in all four seasons of the year. This situation directly affects the culinary culture. Food in the region generally consists of herbaceous plants, grass leaves, thorn tips, vegetables and mushrooms. These are consumed fresh daily during the summer season. Winter foods are prepared as baked dried foods, salted foods, pickles, preserves, molasses and jams, compotes and snacks. Since Giresun is a coastal city, seafood has an important place in its cuisine. Anchovies, whiting, horse mackerel, bonito, mullet, Izmarit, Tirsi, red mullet, Sargan, Kötek and mussels are the most common types. In addition, trout, which grows naturally in our streams, is of great value. In recent years, aquaculture has been developing considerably. In general, Pool Trout and Salmon fish are grown. Depending on the fishing in the highlands and villages, feta cheese, (tecen), leather cheese (tulum), cube cheese and cottage cheese are made. Cube cheese and cottage cheese are buried in the summer in casseroles and stored for the winter. In Giresun cuisine, meals can be made with a few ingredients. Baking beans, cherries coming out of their fruit identity and appearing as food, anchovies in pan, bread, pastry and sometimes in salad constitute other local flavors. Hazelnuts are used not only in cakes, pastries and desserts, but also in meals and appetizers, as well as in folk songs and folk tales. There is such a time as “hazelnut time”. This time is generally known as the arrival time of the expatriate. It is expressed as a time of work, bustle and festivity.

In addition, Giresun-specific molasses bagel (without sesame seeds), which is removed from bread bakeries, attracts attention. It is known that the walnut, hazelnut, çedeneli, and plain pestils made in Şebinkarahisar District are quite delicious. Some of the natural plants in Giresun are dried and used as beverages. These plants are thyme, linden, mint, tea, taflan leaves, rose hips and highland daisies. Apart from these, plenty of tea is grown in our province. In addition to delicious buttermilk, molasses, jam and marmalade are diluted and used as cold drinks. Giresun women, as in everything else, have contributed greatly to the Anatolian culinary culture while creating their own culture with their skills in cooking, developing and presenting hundreds of different kinds of delicious and delicious dishes to the tables.

While 2 main meals, morning and evening, used to be eaten in the Giresun region, these meals have increased to 3. However, regardless of the period, it is seen that tea is brewed in the afternoon and enjoyed with one or two kinds of food products. Sometimes this was just pita bread and fragrant grapes, while other times it was corn bread, dible dishes or a pan dish. This is known to increase the number of meals to 4 today. It is mentioned that in the past, breakfast sometimes started with the morning call to prayer and sometimes it was as late as 8:00 am. In addition, lunchtime meals are eaten between 12:00-13:00, while the evening meal is eaten between 18:30-19:00 on average. This is determined by whether the work in the field, garden or barn is finished. Today, breakfast is eaten between 8:00-9:00 am, lunch between 12:30-13:30 pm, and dinner between 18:30-20:30 pm. In Giresun, an average of half an hour is spent eating. Not much time can be spent at the table due to time-consuming work such as meadow mowing, work intensity in the plateau, tea and hazelnuts. When we look at the food consumed in the region, it is observed that meat was consumed more in both inland and coastal areas, as almost everyone had livestock in the past. Today, since there is very little animal husbandry in the coastal areas, it is possible to say that meat production and consumption are low. It is seen that there are still families engaged in animal husbandry in the inland regions. For this reason, it is possible to say that meat consumption is higher than in coastal areas. Fish consumption is more common especially in coastal areas. It is possible to say that fish consumption is quite low in inland regions. In the inland regions, trout, which is generally grown in fresh waters, is consumed. Very few people consume fish by hunting from the streams. The most common fish dishes are fried anchovy, steamed anchovy, anchovy with vegetables, anchovy pastry (anchovy pilaf) and fried various fish.

Today, since both inland and coastal areas are engaged in field and garden work, it is seen that vegetable and fruit consumption is quite high. Herbal dishes and vegetables are consumed enough to be considered vegetarian. Especially green beans and green peas are grown from vegetables. Beans are used to make piyaz, bean dish, bean roast, bean pickle roast, bean dible, oven bean dishes. At the same time, there are 26 types of mushrooms in Giresun province. Garden mushroom, chicken mushroom, ash mushroom, deer mushroom, bear ear mushroom, evelek mushroom, bitter mushroom are just some examples of these. When looking at fruits, cherry, fig, mulberry, May strawberry, apple, pear, grape, wild pear, cranberry, persimmon, blackberry strawberry, mountain strawberry can be given as examples. Giresun province is known as the homeland of cherries. Giresun is also known as the 'Land of Hazelnuts', which is used as a dried fruit and is an oily seed. Walnuts are grown especially in the inner regions, especially in Şebinkarahisar. Recently, it has been observed that some hazelnut fields have been destroyed and kiwi cultivation has started instead of hazelnuts. It is possible to say that tomato cultivation in Giresun province is very low due to the low number of sunny days. For this reason, tomato paste is used very little in Giresun province cuisine, while pepper paste is almost never used. In the past, everyone produced milk and dairy products in all districts of Giresun, but today it is seen that only people in the inner parts produce their own products. People living in the coastal areas meet their milk, dairy products and egg needs from people who do animal husbandry or from markets selling local products. These products offered for sale in markets selling local products are supplied by villagers producing in the inner regions. While yoghurt used to be added to every meal, today people have abandoned this habit.

In the inland areas, especially in the districts of Şebinkarahisar and Dereli, the people who are engaged in animal husbandry dry the tail fat and preserve it for later use. While these fats and local butters were consumed in the past, today, it is seen that sunflower oil and corn oil sold in markets are also used in addition to local butter. However, it is observed that olive oil has almost no place in Giresun cuisine. In the coastal areas, beans are consumed as a dried legume. Dried beans are obtained by drying the grains obtained from the skins of fresh beans by baking. Dried beans are used especially in dishes such as soup and vegetable roasting in winter. While only corn is produced as a grain in the coastal areas, it has been determined that in the inland areas, grains such as wheat, barley and oats are also grown in addition to corn. In addition, beans are produced as a dried legume in the coastal areas, while in the inland areas, it is seen that in addition to beans, dried legumes such as chickpeas and green lentils are produced. It is possible to say that spice consumption is quite low in Giresun both in the past and today. While only chili pepper, black pepper and mint are used in coastal areas, in addition to these, anuk (mint), mountain mint, mountain thyme, pennyroyal, basil etc. are used in the inner regions. From past to present, compote, compote and ayran have been consumed as the most basic drinks in Giresun province. Especially the must obtained from the grape called 'Scented Grape' is the favorite drink of the region. It is also seen that must made from grape molasses is consumed as a drink. While the herbs that grow naturally in the cuisine of both the inland and coastal regions are used in cooking, it is observed that black cabbage, lettuce and parsley are also grown. It has been determined that the Madımak herb is used in cooking only in the inland regions, fresh and dried.

2.2.1. Local and Traditional Dishes Specific to Giresun

It is seen that the dishes made in both coastal and inland parts of Giresun province are classified as soups, main dishes, dibles, roasted vegetables, desserts and pastries.

2.2.1.1. Soups Specific to Giresun

When it comes to soups, the soups specific to the region are black cabbage soup, corn soup, millet soup, mendek soup, hazelnut flour soup, lamb's ear soup, strawberry soup, black pumpkin soup. In addition to these, especially in the inner regions, ayranlı soup and wheat soup are also made.

2.2.1.2. Main dishes specific to Giresun

When we look at the main dishes of Giresun, we especially come across beetroot (black cabbage). There are dishes such as stuffed black cabbage made with or without meat, black cabbage layer, pezik layer, roasted vegetables, stuffed zucchini, pea dish, nettle dish, keşkek, oven dried, bean dish, hot mushroom stew, zucchini dish with rice, hazelnut meatballs, gelecoş, zucchini yogurt. In addition, especially in the inner regions, stuffed vine leaves and madımak are made.

2.2.1.3. Giresun Special Dilbes

One of the most important dishes of Giresun province is Dible; is a dish prepared by roasting vegetables with onions and then adding rice and cooking. The most common of these are black cabbage dible, bean dible, bean salted dible, pea dible, mushroom dible, vegetable dibles, cherry salted dible, taflan salted dible, pumpkin salted dible, green tomato pickle dible, galdirik dible, mendek dible, anchovy dible.

2.2.1.4. Special Vegetable Roasts for Giresun

It is seen that vegetable and herb roasting has taken its place among the indispensables of Giresun cuisine. The most common ones are Thorn Tip (melevcen) Roast, Galdirik (pickled) Roast, Black Cabbage Roast, Bean Salt (pickled) Roast, Potato Roast.

2.2.1.5. Fried Foods Special to Giresun

It is seen that generally fried Sakarca, fried peas, fried beans with eggs, fried eggplant, fried galdirik are consumed in Giresun province.

2.2.1.6. Giresun's Special Desserts

It is seen that hazelnut burma dessert, hazelnut kadayıf, wire kadayıf, pestil, milky pumpkin dessert are frequently consumed in Giresun.

2.2.1.7. Pastries Special to Giresun

It is seen that water pastry, dry yufka pastry with minced meat and cheese, katmer, siron, famous Giresun cake, Giresun simit, pide are frequently consumed in Giresun.

Today, it is possible to talk about the existence of some flavors that are about to be forgotten in Giresun province. Sometimes because they are difficult and laborious to make and sometimes because of the complacency of being caught up in the changing culinary trends of global culture, our local cultural heritages from the past are gradually losing their importance. There are also foods that are about to be forgotten in Giresun province today. These are known as; Yağlaş, süzme, hedik, pileki bread, haşıl, fetir bread, celecoş, cıratta, yağ ekmek, keşkek. It is also possible to talk about the existence of many types of bread prepared specifically for Giresun. These breads are seen to be; gilik bread, golit bread, beliboh, corn flour bread, anchovy corn bread, pileki bread, yufka, lavaş bread and peksimet.

2.3. Geographically Indicated Foods of Giresun Province

According to Article 34 of the Industrial Property Law No. 6769, a geographical indication is; “A sign indicating a product that is identified with the region, area, region or country of origin in terms of a distinctive feature, reputation or other characteristics.” Geographical indications are divided into two as source indication and origin designation. Source indication is; “Names that identify products originating from a region, area or country with defined geographical boundaries, identified with this geographical area in terms of a distinctive feature, reputation or other characteristics, and at least one of whose production, processing and other operations takes place within the boundaries of the defined geographical area” (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024). There are a total of 12 registered gastronomy products with geographical indications in Giresun province, 5 with source indication and 6 with origin name. These products are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Foods Registered and Receiving Geographical Indication in Giresun Province

Product Name	Registration Date
1. Görele Ice Cream	21.06.2019
2. Alucra Goat Kebab	27.10.2020
3. Giresun Hazelnut Paste	25.08.2020
4. Sergeant Bread	9.12.2020
5. Giresun Kadayif Dessert with Hazelnut Paste	23.03.2023

Source: (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Görele Ice Cream: Görele ice cream, which has been produced with the same formula in Görele for about 200 years, is known as an ice cream that is different from many other local ice creams with its fluid consistency and foamy appearance (Cebeci & Şen, 2020: 215). It is a local ice cream specific to Giresun, prepared using full-fat pasteurized cow's milk, salep, white sugar, water and Glycyrrhiza glabra licorice root extract. Ice cream, which is served on special occasions such as holidays and weddings, continues its traditional feature (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Alucra Goat Kebab: It is a kebab produced by cooking black goats, which are weaned and not older than 1 year, with a carcass weight of 10-15 kg, in the oven with techniques specific to the region, in the period from the beginning of July to the end of October. Alucra Goat Kebab, which has a historical past, is a kebab that is eaten cold. The Alucra district of Giresun province has been determined as the geographical border (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Giresun Hazelnut Paste: In the production of Giresun hazelnut paste, which is produced in the form of sweetened hazelnut paste, Giresun plump hazelnut, Giresun pointed hazelnut and Giresun thick-colored hazelnut, which are produced within geographical borders and have geographical indications, are used. Its preparation is produced by mixing roasted hazelnut with geographical indication and white sugar obtained from sugar beet, which is powdered during production, in certain amounts (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Sergeant Bread: The geographical border is determined as Çavuşlu town of Görele district of Giresun province. It is made by mixing and kneading wheat flour, water and sourdough in a certain ratio and the batter is spread on it after it comes out of the oven. The batter in question gives the bread a shiny appearance and extends the shelf life of the bread (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Giresun Kadayıf Dessert with Hazelnut Paste: It is a kadayıf dessert prepared with hazelnuts and hazelnut paste, special to Giresun.

According to Article 34 of the Industrial Property Law No. 6769, the designation of origin is; “The name given to products originating from a geographically defined region, area or, in exceptional cases, a country, whose entire or essential characteristics derive from natural and human elements specific to this geographical region, and whose production, processing and all other operations take place within the boundaries of this geographical area.” The products with geographical indications that have received a designation of origin in Giresun province are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Foods with Geographical Indication and Name of Origin Registered in Giresun Province

Product Name	Registration Date
1. Giresun Plump Hazelnut	10.10.2001
2. Piraziz Apple	21.12.2016
3. Camoluk Sugar Dried Beans	02.05.2018
4. Giresun Pointed Hazelnut	18.09.2019
5. Giresun Kalinkara Hazelnut/Giresun Karası	18.09.2019
6. Sebinkarahisar Black Mulberry	13.09.2021
7. Giresun Nettle	17.03.2022

Source: (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Giresun Kalinkara Hazelnut / Giresun Karası: It is a hazelnut variety that adapts to different climatic conditions. It is resistant to spring frosts and diseases. It has a gray / brown shell color and an oval-shaped shelled fruit. It differs from other hazelnut varieties in terms of its flavor, quality features, oil / vitamin and mineral values (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Giresun Pointed Hazelnut: In terms of shape; the ripe fruit is flattened on both sides, long and pointed. The fruit shell is shiny, light brown, the tip is relatively off-white with fuzz and an average thickness of 1.05 mm. The fruit shell is thin and easily broken. The membrane on the inner fruit is thin, adherent to the flesh, light shiny brown and veined. The fruit flesh is sweet and crispy, ivory in color (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2024).

Giresun Chubby Hazelnut: It is the most important hazelnut variety grown in Turkey. It is ripe, its fruit is plump and well-shaped. It is a hazelnut variety that is in high demand in international markets due to its very good fruit quality (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, 2024).

Piraziz Apple: It differs from apples grown in other regions with its color, smell, taste and durable structure. It is light green on one side and red on the other (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Çamoluk Sugar Dry Beans: It attracts great attention from the local people and consumers with its unique taste and aroma and cooking in a short time of 15 minutes. The fact that the lands where Çamoluk sugar dry beans, known as "Mindaval guru beans" in the region, are grown are alluvial soils on the banks of streams, soil fertility specific to the region, climate conditions and traditional agricultural techniques have enabled the specialization of the product (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

Developing legal regulations by creating a legal infrastructure for the protection and branding of local products also benefits the development of gastronomy tourism by ensuring the registration of products and the protection of local culinary culture (Değişel, 2021). The fact that the majority of registered geographically indicated products in the destination are gastronomic products is thought to increase the gastronomic tourism potential of the province. In addition, the products for which geographical indication applications have been made are; “Giresun Hazelnut Paste Kadayıf Dessert”, “Giresun Nettle”, “Giresun Pide”, “Giresun Bagel”, “Güce Çayı” and “Şebinkarahisar Black Mulberry”, all of which are produced and consumed as food and beverages in the region. When these products in application status are examined, it can be said that they are products that will enrich the gastronomic tourism of the city. In addition to these products, it is known that application preparations are being made for many gastronomic products.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The qualitative research method was used in the study. Qualitative research is considered as an appropriate approach to deeply understand and examine a specific phenomenon or situation. “Qualitative research aims to discover the subjective perspective of the researcher on the events through the sample, not how the sample sees the events as in quantitative research” (Baydeniz, Kılıcı & Çelik, 2023). Within the scope of the research, it was aimed to determine whether the menus of the food and beverage establishments registered in Giresun province on TripAdvisor included the local and geographical indication registered food and beverage products of Giresun province. Therefore, the menus of the food and beverage establishments and the comments and evaluations directed to the establishments were examined. In the study, 265 restaurant establishments in Giresun and a total of 1,000 comments belonging to these establishments were examined using the content analysis method. In order to examine the restaurant establishments, the pages of the restaurants operating in Giresun on the Tripadvisor travel review site were analyzed. The features of each restaurant were determined by visiting the restaurant page. In the second stage, the comments of the restaurants were examined and the food and beverage names in the comments were determined and counted. The data obtained through content analysis was interpreted. The research was conducted between 01.08.2024-10.11.2024. The reason for examining the Tripadvisor website in the research is that it is the web page with the highest number of clicks among the websites evaluated under the title of "restaurants and food and beverage establishments" (Wakeland, Cholette & Venkat, 2011). The English version of the site was used in the review. The reason for choosing Giresun as the city whose restaurants were examined is that it is among the most attractive destinations with the most local dishes in Turkey (Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, 2024).

In order to examine the restaurants in Giresun province, the city name was searched on the site. Restaurant was selected as the business type displayed in the city. Scoring criterion was used for the ranking of the restaurants. Thus, the page was shown the restaurants with the best score averages. No filter was used other than these options. The purpose of using the score ranking is to use the ones that users are likely to encounter. Because even if the show only nearby restaurants command is used for visitors using the application of this website, it lists the restaurants near them first according to the score criterion. The first 265 restaurants of each city on the website's list were included in the review. The last 50 comments of each restaurant, the latest dated November 10, 2024, were examined. These comments were recorded on August 1 and an offline evaluation was made. The information about each comment was marked on the created checklist. The review was conducted by two researchers. In order to determine the food and beverage names in the comments, all words were evaluated with content analysis, and the resulting word counts and food and beverage names were used among the words. The names of the dishes were directly noted to avoid any interpretation differences, and the names of the foods and drinks written in different letters or words were combined.

4. FINDINGS

Within the scope of the research, descriptive information is presented about the menus of the businesses in Giresun province and the local products included in the guest comments. The total number of businesses whose comments and menus were examined in the research is 265 and 1000 comments about these businesses were examined. One of the main objectives of the research was to examine the dish names related to Giresun local cuisine and geographically indicated products in the comments. In addition, it was seen that the most mentioned local dishes in restaurant menus and guest comments were 24. These dishes are; cheese pita, minced meat pita, pita with kashar kavurma, observatory's famous pita, nettle, beet soup, roasted mushroom, corn bread, sirgan oil, roasted pickles, shredded wheat with milk, roasted bean pickle, pilaf with anchovy, cabbage Dible, cabbage sarma, thorn tip, sakarca roast, Görelî ice cream, nettle manti,

nettle soup, merulcan, taftan salted, cherry salted, wrapped shredded wheat with hazelnut paste. Among the 1,000 comments examined, the number of comments without a food name is 225. The number of comments with only one food name was 272, the number of comments with two food names was 150, the number of comments with three food names was 90, the number of comments with four food names was 40, and the number of comments with six food names was 223. When the first food and drink names encountered in the comments are examined; Pide 100, Kebab 40, Pizza 50, Breakfast 35, Lamb meat 45, Ayran are the first food and drink names encountered 2 times. 150 comments among the examined comments contain two types of food and drink names. The most used food and drink names as second food names in the comments are as follows: Nettle soup 25, anchovy pilaf 16, pickle roast 15, wrapped kadayıf dessert with hazelnut paste 30 and cherry salting 20, taftan salting 16, beet soup 20, milk kadayıf 28. When the second food names are examined, the dessert and salad eaten after the main course draw attention. Some visitors may also tend to write all the meals they eat. Therefore, using their main meals and the dessert and salad they eat afterwards or together in their comments can be attributed to the commentator profile. The most mentioned foods and beverages in total in the comments were determined as; Pide 150, Lahana diblesi 50, anchovy pilaf 40, sirgan oil 25, pickle kavurma 35, thorn tip 20, sakarca kavurma 30, Göreli ice cream 30, merulcan 23. Again, pide and kebab were at the top of the list of the most striking dishes. Appetizers, which are occasionally offered as treats in Giresun local restaurants, are appreciated by visitors. Appetizers in the cold type, which are an important part of Turkish culinary culture, are usually in flavors that can be easily liked as an appetizer. Appetizer culture can be used in the marketing of gastronomy as a reflection of the Turkish culinary culture. Dessert and tea have been widely included in the comments as accompanying items to meals.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The aim of this study is to analyze the usage status of geographically indicated products specific to Giresun province in the menus of food and beverage establishments in Giresun province on TripAdvisor in the context of gastronomy tourism and the food included in guest comments. Giresun has a rich culinary tradition with its historical and cultural heritage. In this context, the potential of geographically indicated products, which have an important place in Giresun cuisine, in terms of gastronomy tourism was evaluated. It is thought that the use of emblems belonging to products with geographical indications that have registered source and origin indications in Giresun province will enable the products to be known, marketed and distinguished from other products. The use of registered geographical indications shows that the products are different from other products, can ensure that they are preferred compared to other products and even create brand value. Although the competitive power of Giresun province in terms of meat products is seen as weak compared to other regions, the existence of a product with geographical indication such as “Alucra Oğlak Kebabı” and the introduction of products such as “Hazelnut Meatballs” and “Hazelnut Grilled Meatballs” that can be used as ingredients in products with geographical indications in addition to this geographically indicated product should contribute to the elimination of the deficiency in this area. There are many cities in Turkey that stand out with their gastronomic products and many kebab-meatball varieties that have received geographical indications. In addition, the awareness of these products and their contribution to the city they are located in are quite high. Products such as “Adana Kebab”, “Cağ Kebab”, “Büryan Kebab” are products that are known and found in the menus of accommodation and food and beverage establishments in the geography they are located in. However, a product with a geographical indication such as “Alucra Oğlak Kebab” is rarely found in the menus of accommodation and food and beverage establishments in Giresun province. Hazelnuts have a special place in the destination. Hazelnut trees are known as the “Hazelnut Hearth” in the region. It can be said that the biggest reason for this is that it is the most important economic source of income in the region. “Giresun Kalınkara Hazelnut”, “Giresun Sivri Hazelnut” and “Giresun Chubby Hazelnut” grown in Giresun province are products with geographical indication. It is foreseen that the promotion and marketing of these products and the foods produced from these products will make a great contribution to both the regional economy and the national economy. In order to provide this contribution, it is thought that local businesses should include hazelnuts and local dishes and desserts containing hazelnuts, and that their promotion and product range will contribute more economically to the destination. It is important to increase public support and supervision, especially for the protection and promotion of products with geographical indications. In addition, the completion of the Hazelnut Museum, which has been planned for Giresun province for many years, and the emphasis on products with geographical indications in the museum will contribute to regional gastronomy tourism. Giresun province, which acts with the slogan “Homeland of Cherry, Capital of Hazelnut”, has not yet reached the desired point in terms of gastronomy tourism. The city, which has many local flavors due to its geographical structure and cultural and social structure from the past to the present, needs to give

importance to marketing activities in the field of gastronomy tourism. In the destination, which has twelve products with geographical indications in gastronomy terms and where applications have been made for many other products with gastronomy value, it is seen that products with geographical indications cannot be used effectively in terms of tourism. Products with geographical indications are considered to be an important factor affecting the choice of destination by tourists, especially in terms of gastronomy tourism.

In Giresun province, products that are considered to be applied for geographical indication should receive support from different scientific fields and cooperation should be established with experts on geographical indications. Recipes and information of all local dishes and products of the province should be prepared, incentives should be provided for local businesses to include them in their menus and the original recipes of these local dishes should be recorded. It is thought that the attractiveness of the destination can be increased by applying for geographical indication for suitable products later.

REFERENCES

- Ab Karim, S., & Chi, C. G. Q. (2010). Culinary tourism as a destination attraction: An empirical examination of destinations' food image. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 19(6), 531-555.
- Akgöl, Y. (2012). *Gastronomi turizmi ve Türkiye'yi ziyaret eden yabancı turistlerin gastronomi deneyimlerinin değerlendirilmesi* [Yüksek lisans tezi, Mersin Üniversitesi]. YÖK Ulusal Tez Merkezi.
- Aksoy, M., & Sezgi, G. (2015). Gastronomi turizmi ve Güneydoğu Anadolu Bölgesi gastronomik unsurları. *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 3(3), 79-89.
- Apak, Ö. C., & Gürbüz, A. (2023). The effect of local food consumption of domestic tourists on sustainable tourism. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 71, 103192.
- Avşar, M., & Eryılmaz, B. (2022). Coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin Amasya turizminin gelişimine katkısının değerlendirilmesi. *Türk Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(4), 988-1003.
- Baydeniz, E., Kılıcı, L., & Çelik, S. (2023). Yerel mutfak algısı gastro aktivite ve gastro deneyimin destinasyon marka imajına etkisi: Afyonkarahisar örneği. *Safran Kültür ve Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(1), 133-153.
- Belisle, F. J. (1983). Tourism and food production in the Caribbean. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 10(4), 497-513.
- Belpınar, A. (2014). *Gastronomi turizmine yönelik turist görüşlerinin kültürlerarası karşılaştırılması: Kapadokya örneği* [Yüksek lisans tezi, Muğla Sıtkı Koçman Üniversitesi]. YÖK Ulusal Tez Merkezi.
- Çapar, G., & Yenipınar, U. (2016). Somut olmayan kültürel miras kaynağı olarak yöresel yiyeceklerin turizm endüstrisinde kullanılması. *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 4(1), 100-115.
- Çavuş, O., & Eker, Ş. (2022). Coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin sürdürülebilir gastronomi turizmi bağlamında değerlendirilmesi: Bolu Kanlıca Mantarı, Mengen örneği. *Türk Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(1), 303-320.
- Dağ, T. (2020). *Geleneksel peynirlerin gastronomi turizmi açısından değerlendirilmesi: İzmir örneği*, Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli Üniversitesi, Nevşehir.
- De Miguel Molina, M., de Miguel Molina, B., Santamarina Campos, V., & del Val Segarra Oña, M. (2016). Intangible heritage and gastronomy: The impact of UNESCO gastronomy elements. *Journal of Culinary Science & Technology*, 14(4), 293-310.
- Denk, E., & Bilici, N. S. (2021). Erzurum ilinin coğrafi işaret (Ci) almış ürünlerinin gastronomi turizmi kapsamında değerlendirilmesi. *Gastroia: Journal of Gastronomy and Travel Research*, 5(1), 102-122.
- Dilsiz, B. (2010). *Türkiye'de gastronomi ve turizm: İstanbul örneği* [Yüksek lisans tezi, İstanbul Üniversitesi]. YÖK Ulusal Tez Merkezi.
- Duram, L., & Oberholtzer, L. (2010). A geographic approach to place and natural resource use in local food systems. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 25(2), 99-108.

- Doğancılı, O. S. (2020). GAP turlarında coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin kullanımına ilişkin içerik analizi, *Uluslararası Türk Dünyası Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 5(2): 246-258.
- Ertan, A. (2010). Prestijli tarım ürünlerinin pazarlanmasında kalite ve coğrafi işaret kavramlarının tutundurulması ve bu bağlamda tarım satış kooperatiflerinin önemi. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (12): 157-170.
- Figueiredo, E. (2021). Rural provenance food as cultural heritage: A way of promoting territorial development?. In A. Covas, R. Rodrigues, P. A. Silva, & F. Teles (Eds.), *Handbook of research on cultural heritage and its impact on territory innovation and development*, 114-137.
- Göker, G. (2011). *Destinasyon çekicilik unsuru olarak gastronomi turizmi* (Balıkesir ili örneği) [Yüksek lisans tezi, Balıkesir Üniversitesi]. YÖK Ulusal Tez Merkezi.
- Güngör, A., & Kök, A. (2021). Coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin sürdürülebilir gastronomi turizmi açısından önemi: Akçakoca-Melengüceği tatlısı örneği. *Gastroia: Journal of Gastronomy and Travel Research*, 5(1), 61-74.
- Güngör, O. (2022). Sürdürülebilir gastronomi turizmi bağlamında coğrafi işaret: Aydın Bozdoğan Olukbaşı oğlak çevirme kebabı örneği. *Nazilli İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 3(2), 84-92.
- Harrington, R. J., & Ottenbacher, M. C. (2010). Culinary tourism—A case study of the gastronomic capital. *Journal of Culinary Science & Technology*, 8(1), 14-32.
- Hazarhun, E., & Tepeci, M. (2018). Coğrafi işarete sahip olan yöresel ürün ve yemeklerin Manisa'nın gastronomi turizminin gelişimine katkısı. *Güncel Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(1), 371-389.
- Kan, M., Gülçubuk, B., & Küçükçongar, M. (2012). Coğrafi işaretlerin kırsal turizmde kullanımla olanakları. *KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 14(22), 93-101.
- Karahan, G. (2019). *Gastronomi turizminin yerel halk üzerindeki algısı ve sürdürülebilirliği: Giresun ili örneği* [Yüksek lisans tezi, İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi]. YÖK Ulusal Tez Merkezi.
- Kattiyapornpong, U., Ditta-Apichai, M., & Chuntamara, C. (2022). Exploring gastronomic tourism experiences through online platforms: Evidence from Thai local communities. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 47(3), 241-257.
- Kodaş, D., & Dikici, E. (2012). Ahlat kırsal bölgesinde gastronomi turizminin muhtemel toplumsal etkileri üzerine nitel bir çalışma. *Aksaray Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 4(2), 51-68.
- Küçükaltan, G. (2009, Nisan). Küreselleşme sürecinde gastronomide yöresel tatların turistlerin destinasyon tercihlerine ve ülke ekonomilerine etkileri. 3. Ulusal Gastronomi Sempozyumu Bildirileri, Antalya, Türkiye.
- Küçükkömürler, S., Şırvan, N. B., & Sezgin, A. C. (2018). Dünyada ve Türkiye'de gastronomi turizmi. *Uluslararası Turizm Ekonomi ve İşletme Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(2), 78-85.
- Laenko, L. V. (2021). Gastronomic realias though intercultural interaction. In O. O. Boriskina (Ed.), *Алексева е. А.*, 320-328.
- Mariani, M., Casabianca, F., Cerdan, C. and Peri, I. (2021). Protecting Food Cultural Biodiversity: From Theory to Practice. Challenging the Geographical Indications and the Slow, Food Models, *Sustainability*, 13, 5265.
- Matviichuk, L. Y., Lepkyi, M. I., Dashchuk, Y. Y., Sydoruk, S. V., & Mezentseva, I. V. (2022). Approach to formation of enogastronomic tourism based on the geographical indication system. *Journal of Geology, Geography and Geoecology*, 31(4), 689-701.
- Mercan, Ş. O., & Üzülmöz, M. (2014). Coğrafi işaretlerin bölgesel turizm gelişimindeki önemi: Çanakkale ili örneği. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi İktisadi İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 29(2), 67-94.
- Özdemir, G. ve Altınar, D. D. (2018). *Türkiye'de üretilen coğrafi işaret ile tescillenmiş peynir çeşitleri*. Uluslararası Gastronomi Turizmi Araştırmaları Kongresi, Kocaeli, Türkiye, 631-640.
- Özdemir, G. ve Altınar, D.D. (2019). Gastronomi kavramları ve gastronomi turizmi üzerine bir inceleme, *Erzincan Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 12(1): 1-14.

- Pillay, S. K., Sigamany, V., & Belwal, M. (2018). Geographical indication: An exploratory examination on GI tagging Indian food in opening avenues to develop culinary/gastronomic tourism. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology (IOSR-JESTFT)*, 12(10), 60-68.
- Piramanayagam, S., & Seal, P. P. (2022). Geographical indication (GI) tagged foods and promotion of gastronomic tourism: A developing country perspective. In H. Oktadiana, M. Rahmanita, R. Suprina, & P. Junyang (Eds.), *Current issues in tourism, gastronomy, and tourist destination research*, Routledge, 393-399.
- Rasmi, A. A., Phuoc, J. C., Othman, Z., & Azman, N. (2022). Geographical indication for gastronomy tourism: Maximising intellectual property value and branding. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 21(2), 1-13.
- Quan, S., & Wang, N. (2004). Towards a structural model of the tourist experience: An illustration from food experiences in tourism. *Tourism Management*, 25(3), 297-305.
- Sabur, D. G., & Güneş, S. G. (2023). Kayseri Bünyan ve Akkışla gilaburusu örneğinde coğrafi işaret tescili ve gastronomi turizmi. *Gastroia: Journal of Gastronomy and Travel Research*, 7(1), 141-156.
- Şimşek, A., & Güleç, E. (2020). Gastronomi turizmi kapsamında coğrafi işaretli ürün: Elazığ Orciği. *Aydın Gastronomy*, 4(2), 73-81.
- Süslü, C., Eryılmaz, G., & Demir, E. (2020). Coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin gastronomi kapsamında değerlendirilmesi: Mersin ili örneği. *Journal of Recreation and Tourism Research*, 7(2), 135-149.
- Tekelioğlu, Y. (2019). Coğrafi işaretler ve Türkiye uygulamaları. *Ufuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 8(15), 47-75.
- Tuncay, N., & Özcan, C. (2022). Gastronominin yerel ekonomiler üzerindeki etkileri. *Turizm ve Rekreasyon Akademik Çalışmalar Dergisi*, (32), 31-45.
- Tüfekci, Ö. K., Tüfekci, N., ve Kalkan, G. (2016). Eğirdir mutfağının marka kimlik unsurlarının değerlendirilmesi. Menülere ilişkin bir içerik analizi, Uluslararası Multidisipliner Konferansı. Antalya, Türkiye, 218-225.
- Türk Patent ve Marka Kurumu. (2024). Coğrafi işaret nedir?[Online] <https://www.ci.gov.tr/sayfa/co%C4%9Fafi-i%C5%9Faret-nedir>> (Erişim Tarihi: 01.11.2024). Türk Patent ve Marka Kurumu. (2024). Coğrafi işaretler veritabanı.[Online] <https://ci.turkpatent.gov.tr/veri-tabani>> (Erişim Tarihi: 01.11.2024).
- Torusdağ, G. B., Önem, E. Ö., Sami, F., & Kızıldemir, Ö. (2022). Yerel mutfakların gastronomi turizmi çerçevesinde değerlendirilmesi. *Journal of Gastronomy, Hospitality and Travel*, 5(1), 66-82.
- Yıldız, M. H. (2021). *Coğrafi işaretli ürünlerin bölge halkı tarafından bilinirliğinin gastronomi turizmi kapsamında değerlendirilmesi: Isparta örneği* [Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Kocaeli Üniversitesi].
- Yıkılmış, S., and Ünal, A. (2016). The Importance of geographical indication in gastronomytourism: Turkey, *International Journal of Agricultural and Life Science*, 2(4): 73-
- Yurt, İ., Bayraklı, B., & Özengi, M. (2024). Gastronomi Turizminin Sürdürülebilirliğinde Turist Rehberlerinin Rolü. *Journal of Academic Tourism Studies*, 5(1), 61-78.